

A $\pm 0.5V$ BiCMOS Class-A Current Conveyor

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Abstract—In this paper, a new BiCMOS CCII and CCCII, capable of operate at $\pm 0.5V$ and having wide dynamic range with achieved bandwidth of 480MHz and 430MHz respectively have been proposed. The structures have been found to be insensitive to the threshold voltage variations. The proposed circuits are suitable for implementation using $0.25\mu m$ BiCMOS technology. Pspice simulations confirm the performance of the proposed structures.

Keywords—BiCMOS, Current conveyor, Compound current conveyor, Low supply voltage, Threshold voltage variation.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Current Conveyor II (CCII) has the unique feature of having both low and high impedance input port, a port generally termed as port X which serves as low input port for input current and output voltage. The low input impedance port is suitable for current mode structures, and high input impedance port suitable for voltage mode operation. Similarly it has high output impedance port for current mode structures and low output impedance port suitable for voltage mode operations. Hence a CCII is more versatile and can be used to process both current and voltage signals [1]-[8].

A CC is a grounded three-port network as shown in Fig.1. and it's characteristic is given as

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y \\ V_x \\ I_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \pm 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_y \\ I_x \\ V_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where X and Y are the input ports and Z is the output port.

Fig. 1 CCII+ block diagram

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The bipolar transistors have higher transconductance (g_m) and high frequency performance over their CMOS counterparts [9]. Advantage of MOSFET includes high input impedance, low power consumption, and small silicon area [10]. In BiCMOS structures the advantage of the both technology have been utilized. In this paper a new CCII and Compound current conveyor (CCCII) structures suitable for integration in BiCMOS technology and capable of operate at ultra low voltage of $\pm 0.5V$ have been proposed. The structures have a wide current bandwidth of 480MHz for class-A CC and 430MHz for class-A CCC with power consumption of 0.80mW and 1.0mW respectively.

II. PROPOSED $\pm 0.5V$ CLASS-A BICMOS CCII REALIZATION

The proposed BiCMOS realization for the low voltage CCII is shown in Fig. 2. The circuit has been designed using MOSFETs and BJTs in order to get the requirement of low power supply and low power dissipation. The input stage and current source have been realized through MOSFETs so that the high input impedance structure can be implemented. In order to operate at a low voltage and reducing power supply, bipolar current mirror is used because it has larger dynamic range [10]-[11]. Furthermore, it has superior high frequency performance then their CMOS counterpart [9].

The groups of the transistors (M1 and M2), (Q3 and Q4), (Q7-Q9), as well as (M11 and M12) are matched. All the MOSFETs operate in saturation region, while all the BJTs in active region. M10, M11, M12, and M13 serve as DC current sources. The current mirroring has been achieved by Q3 and Q4 forces equal currents I_B in M1 and M2, there by resulting in equal gate to source voltage This forces voltage at port X to follow the impressed voltage at port Y Mirroring action between Q7 and Q9, and M12 and M14 transfer I_x to I_{z+} .

Fig. 2 Proposed Low Voltage BiCMOS Class-A CCII

The threshold voltage variation caused by the body effect of MOS transistors are negligible owing to the fact that except M1, M2 and M6, all the MOSFETs have sources that are connected to the positive or negative supply rail. Threshold voltage variations of transistors (M1 and M2) are canceled out

Fig. 4 Static characteristics of the conveyor voltage transfer function

Fig. 8 Amplitude characteristics of the conveyor current transfer function I_Z/I_X [dB]

Fig. 5 Voltage transfer error at X port

Fig. 9 Amplitude characteristics of the current transfer function I_{Z+}/I_X [dB]

Fig. 6 Input port X characteristics

Fig. 10 Static characteristics of the conveyor current transfer function from I_{Z+} to I_X

Fig. 7 Static characteristics of the conveyor current transfer function from I_{Z+} to I_X

Fig. 11 Static characteristics of the conveyor current transfer function from I_{Z-} to I_X

TABLE II
BASIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PROPOSED CCII AND CCCII

Parameters	Class-A CCII Operation	Class-AB CCCII operation
Supply Voltage	$\pm 0.5V$	$\pm 0.5V$
Current Gain	1.0	1.0
Voltage Gain	0.96	0.96
Current TR band width	480MHz	430MHz
Output resistance at port Rz	4.7K Ω	4.7K Ω
Input resistance at port Rx	2.57 Ω	2.57 Ω
Input resistance at port Ry	1.0E20Ohm	1.0E20Ohm
Power dissipation	0.80mW	1.0mW
Voltage range	-0.5V to +0.5V	-0.5V to +0.5V
Current Range	-125 μA to +125 μA	-125 μA to +125 μA

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed current conveyor structures can operate at ultra low voltage of $\pm 0.5V$ and have, bandwidths of 480MHz for class-A CCII and of 430MHz for class-A CCCII, wide dynamic range of rail to rail ($-0.5V$ to $+0.5V$) for both the structures, and low power dissipation. The proposed structures are suitable for the low voltage, low power VLSI Applications.

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